

THE VERB IN GERMAN AND THE DIFFICULTIES OF LEARNING IT

Yusifli A.

*Ganja State University
Ganja, Azerbaijan*

ABSTRACT

In German, the verb is one of the main parts of speech. It is used to express actions, states, processes, and changes.

The study of the verb in German includes several stages:

Familiarity with the main types of verbs. In German, verbs can be weak (in which the infinitive ends in -en) and strong (have variable vowels). It is necessary to study the main types of verbs, their conjugation in different tenses and features of declension.

The study of verb tenses. In German, there is a wide range of tenses, including the present, past, future tense, as well as various types of conditional and subjunctive moods. At this stage, it is necessary to study the main time forms and their use.

Vocabulary expansion. To use a variety of verb constructions, it is necessary to study a large number of verbs and their meanings, as well as to study the various grammatical constructions in which verbs can be used.

Practice and practice of the use of verbs in speech. While studying verbs, it is important to actively use them in various contexts in order to consolidate their correct use and learn to freely express their thoughts and actions.

The stages of learning a verb in German can be different depending on the level of the language and the teaching methodology, but these main stages allow you to create a framework for learning verbs and their use in speech.

Keywords: teaching methods, strong and weak verbs, modal verbs.

There are several types of verbs in German:

Strong (starke Verben) are verbs whose verb base changes in the past tense and past participle. Examples: kommen (come) - kam (come) - gekommen (come), sehen (see) - sah (saw) - gesehen (seen).

Weak (schwache Verben) are verbs in which the past tense and the past participle are formed by adding the ending "-te" or "-et" to the verb base. Examples: arbeiten (work) - arbeitete (worked) - gearbeitet (worked), spielen (play) - spielte (played) - gespielt (played).

Auxiliary verbs (helfende Verben) are verbs that are used in combination with other verbs to form complex tenses. The most common auxiliary verbs in German are sein (to be) and haben (to have). Examples: ich bin gegangen (I went), du hast gesehen (you saw).

Impersonal (unsönliche Verben) are verbs that are used without personal pronouns. The most common impersonal verbs in German are es gibt (is), es regnet (it's raining).

Reflexive (reflexive Verben) are verbs that express actions performed by the subject himself, and require the use of the pronominal pronoun "self" (sich) in the complement. Examples: sich waschen (to wash), sich freuen (to rejoice).

Modal (modal Verben) are verbs that express ability, necessity, desire or permission. The most well-known modal verbs in German are können (to be able), müssen (must), wollen (to want), sollen (must), dürfen (to have permission).

Irregular (unregelmäßige Verben) are verbs that do not follow the general rules of declension and form change. Their forms cannot be derived from the base word. Examples: sein (to be), haben (to have), werden (to become), wissen (to know).

From a semantic point of view, it is. verb. they are classified as follows:

Indefinite verbs - they express an action or state, but do not specify it. Examples: sein (to be), haben (to have), werden (to become).

Transitive verbs - they require an additional object to which the action is directed. Examples: sehen (see), lesen (read), kaufen (buy).

Intransitive verbs - they do not require an additional object and express a state or action that occurs without direction to anyone or anything. Examples: schlafen (sleep), gehen (walk), lachen (laugh).

A state is a verb that expresses a permanent or temporary state. Examples: lieben (to love), hassen (to hate), wissen (to know).

Two-part verbs - consist of a main verb and a preposition or adverb. Examples: ankommen (to arrive), mitbringen (to bring with you), umgehen (to make do).

Phrasal verbs - consist of a main verb and a preposition/adverb, and have a specific meaning. Examples: aufstehen (to get up), abfahren (to go), einladen (to invite).

Auxiliary verbs are used in combination with other verbs to form the tenses of a verb or to form a passive form. Examples: sein (to be), haben (to have), werden (to become).

From a morphological point of view, the following verbs are distinguished in German:

Weak verbs: They form the past tense and participles by adding suffixes to the verb base. For example: spielen (play) - spielte (played), gespielt (died).

Strong verbs: They change the verb base to form the past tense and participles. For example: gehen (go) - ging (went), gegangen (went).

There are also irregular verbs that do not obey the general rules of declension and form past tense and participle forms incorrectly. For example: sein (be) - war (was), gewesen (was).

Behind the word formation in the German language, the following verbs are distinguished how:

Verbals (trennbare Verben): These are verbs that can be divided into two parts. For example: ankommen (to come, to arrive), abholen (to pick up), aufstehen (to get up).

Non-verbal (untrennbare Verben): these are verbs that cannot be divided into two parts. For example: verstehen (to understand), besuchen (to visit), machen (to do).

Compound (zusammengesetzte Verben): These are verbs that consist of two or more words. For example: einkaufen gehen (go shopping), fernsehen (watch TV), Rad fahren (ride a bike).

Prefixes (präfixverben): these are verbs that have a prefix that changes their meaning. For example: mitbringen (bring with you), umziehen (move), kennenlernen (get acquainted).

Suffixal (suffixverben): These are verbs that are modified by adding suffixes. For example: arbeiten (to work) - sich anstrengen (to try).

Shortened (kürzungsverben): these are verbs that are shortened by dropping part of a word. For example: machen (do) - mach (do).

These are just some of the different types of verbs in German. There are many other rules and features of word formation in the German language. Learning a verb in German can be difficult due to several main reasons:

Verbs have many forms and conjugations. The German language has six tenses and four verb conjugations, each of which has its own rules and exceptions. It is often difficult for students of this language to remember all these forms and rules.

There are a large number of irregular verbs that have unpredictable changes in the basic forms. This greatly complicates the study and application of these verbs in the right contexts.

In German, there are various ways of forming tenses, including the use of auxiliary verbs and changes in the main verbs. It can be difficult for German language learners to figure out how to correctly form the right tense or verb form.

For a better explanation and study of the verb in German, you can use the following methods:

Systematic study of conjugations and rules of verbs. Well-organized German language textbooks offer step-by-step study of conjugations and rules, which allows students to study verbs more consciously and structurally.

Practice and repetition. Regular use of verbs in speech and writing allows you to consolidate the basic forms and rules. A variety of verb conjugation exercises will also help improve the understanding and application of verbs.

Learning irregular verbs. Irregular verbs in German must be memorized separately. Their list can be found in textbooks or online resources. Gradually learning and repeating these verbs can help you master their proper use.

The use of various sources of information and materials. Video tutorials, audio recordings, interactive exercises and even a conversation with native speakers will help you to understand and apply verbs more deeply in practice.

A variety of practical situations. Tasks and exercises related to specific situations from real life will help the student to apply verbs in realistic contexts and better memorize their use.

Learning a verb in German requires patience and practice, but with the help of a systematic approach and a variety of methods, it can be successfully mastered.

References

1. М.И. Марфинская, И. Монахова, Грамматика немецкого языка Учебное пособие, МОСКВА, ЮРИСТЪ, 2001. стр. 18-27
2. Волина С.А., Секреты немецкой грамматики, Морфология, Учебное пособие ОНИКС, 2004.
3. Рыжова Е.В. ГРАММАТИКА НЕМЕЦКОГО ЯЗЫКА (В ТАБЛИЦАХ И СХЕМАХ) Учебно-методическое пособие. ПЕНЗА, 2016
4. Е.В. Лаврищева DEUTSCHE GRAMMATIK: WARUM NICHT? Учебно-методическое пособие. Елец – 2021
5. Нефёдов Сергей Трофимович. Теоретическая грамматика немецкого языка. Морфология. Издательство: Санкт-Петербургский государственный университет. 2018